

Looking at the Trees to See the Forest: Construal Level Shift in Strategic Problem Framing and Formulation

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1 | INTRODUCTION

To launch the strategic decision-making process, managers first need to identify a strategic problem or opportunity¹, and then decide what to do about it (Csaszar and Laureiro-Martínez 2018, Mintzberg et al. 1976, Nickerson and Argyres 2018). This task is difficult because strategic problems tend to be complex and ill-structured (Camillus 2008, Lyles 1981), often manifesting only through symptoms – observable deviations from performance expectations (Cyert and March 1963). These symptoms are the result of various, potentially interrelated causes (i.e., complex, Simon 1991), many of which are not known ex ante (i.e., ill-structured, Fernandez and Simon 1999). When engaging in the strategic decision-making process, managers tackling strategic problems benefit from developing theories about the causes of such problems – i.e., from formulating the problem – if they are to avoid solving mere symptoms (Csaszar and Ostler 2020, Nickerson and Argyres 2018, March and Simon 1958).

The behavioral view of the firm typically describes managers as focusing on local symptoms to isolate a readily identifiable cause and expanding the search for other causes only when the initial solution fails (Cyert and March 1963, Greve 2003, Joseph and Gaba 2020, Posen et al. 2018). However, in strategic contexts, each solution or strategy takes significant resources and time to develop and execute (Mintzberg et al. 1976) – resources that are costly and limited and time that allows the problem to morph. Furthermore, this local search tends to result in suboptimal, incremental solutions close to the starting point of the search process (Foss et al. 2016, Gavetti and Levinthal 2000, Kittur et al. 2019, Nickerson and Zenger 2004). To address this issue, scholars have emphasized the importance of problem formulation and its comprehensiveness, or the number of potentially relevant causes theorized during the formulation activity (Baer et al. 2013). Comprehensive problem formulation serves as a map of the problem space so that managers can better evaluate what may be central causes and find globally optimal solutions (Camuffo et al. 2020, 2024a, 2024b, Gavetti and Levinthal 2000, Gavetti et al. 2005, Ott and Eisenhardt 2020, Valentine et al. 2024). Yet, how managers can derive such maps is not well understood.

¹ We use the term “problems” to refer to both problems and opportunities (see Baer et al. 2013).

Research that takes a cognitive view on problem formulation indicates that abstract thinking is critical for comprehensive problem formulation (Park and Baer 2022). Complex, ill-structured problems typically have a wide range of causes, from obvious to more hidden ones that managers can easily overlook (e.g., Simon 1991, Rumelt 2011). Concrete thinking during problem formulation may lead managers to end up “in the weeds” and fixate on obvious, easily identifiable causes (see Gilbert et al. 1998, Shani et al. 2009). Abstract, “big picture” thinking allows managers to step back and think flexibly about potential causes, allowing them to identify both common and novel causes of the problem².

Research on attention, however, indicates that abstract thinking also has an important weakness. Comprehensiveness is a result of two interrelated activities, problem framing and problem formulation (Ananth et al. 2024). Problem framing involves a process of attention allocation toward symptoms. Symptoms are the empirical building blocks – the necessary informational cues – that allow managers to theorize what might be the causes of the problem. Problem formulation is largely concerned with theorizing or causal judgment based on the symptoms unearthed during the framing activity (Baer et al. 2013, Brunswik 1952, Csaszar and Levinthal 2016, Gigerenzer et al. 1991, Park 2024). Abstract thinking can encourage managers to use schema-driven attention (Joseph and Wilson 2018, Henderson 2013, McCrea et al. 2012, Milkman et al. 2012, Ocasio 2011), which can lead them to only attend to symptoms that fit into their existing and validated schemas (e.g., key performance indicators). Consequently, abstract thinking during problem framing may filter out uncommon, unique (novel) symptoms particular to the problem at hand, which may lead managers to overlook relevant, potentially central causes of strategic problems (Grimes and Vogus 2021, Nickerson et al. 2007, Park 2024).

In this paper, we propose a *construal level shift model* (Steinbach et al. 2019, Wiesenfeld et al. 2017) and claim that both concrete *and* abstract thinking are needed for comprehensive problem formulation, but at different stages. According to this theory, construal levels, or the degree of abstraction

² Given past research (Park and Baer 2022), we assume that managers have a baseline of epistemic motivation (i.e., the desire to learn about complex, ill-structured problems such that they are willing to engage in problem framing and formulation rather than immediately reacting to symptoms to reach closure prematurely).

in cognition, influence both attention allocation and theorization (Trope and Liberman 2010, Wiesenfeld et al. 2017). Our model's central proposition is that comprehensive problem formulation is more likely when managers first frame problems using a low construal level to increase the number of symptoms they attend to and then switch to a high construal level when formulating problems.

A low construal level allows individuals to examine issues from a closer psychological distance and focus "their attention on the unique and idiosyncratic demands of present circumstances" (Wiesenfeld et al. 2017: 369). Therefore, during problem framing, low construal thinking may enable managers to engage in stimulus-driven attention (Joseph and Wilson 2018, van Kerckhove et al. 2015), perceiving the full range of symptoms without schemas as filters and increasing the number of symptoms managers attend to (i.e., symptom count). We posit that a greater symptom count is key to increasing the likelihood of identifying alternative, potentially relevant causes, particularly when managers formulate problems using high construal level thinking. For example, identifying operational issues across different products may help managers theorize about causes related to protocols and operational policies, and complaints from the past and current employees may suggest issues with the culture of the organization. We maintain that a high construal level enables managers to step back and combine these symptoms at a greater psychological distance so that they can formulate problems more comprehensively.

We empirically examine our model with three studies, two experiments with working individuals and mid- to high-level managers in large organizations and a correlational study with executives. The results support our construal level shift model, and post-hoc analyses of our studies offer insight into the mechanisms of the model. During problem framing, low construal thinking helped managers find both novel (less common, often overlooked) *and* common symptoms, increasing the overall symptom count. During problem formulation, a high construal level increased the likelihood that individuals identified both common *and* novel causes from available symptoms, increasing comprehensiveness.

Our research contributes to the behavioral and knowledge-based views of the firm and the theory-based view of strategy (Ehrig and Schmidt 2022, Nickerson and Zenger 2004, Posen et al. 2018, Wuebker et al. 2023). Researchers in these areas consider the comprehensiveness of problem formulation to be a

central antecedent of effective strategies, exploration, knowledge creation, and performance (Camuffo et al. 2024a, 2024b, Felin and Zenger 2009, Felin et al. 2015, Nickerson et al. 2007, Nickerson and Argyres 2018, Posen et al. 2018). Our paper offers insights into how to frame and formulate strategic problems with greater comprehensiveness and, correspondingly, novelty. In addition, our paper contributes to managerial cognition research. We challenge the view that concrete thinking is conducive to only minor issues, such as the implementation of developed strategies (Carton 2018, Steinbach et al. 2019, Park and Baer 2022). Instead, our model highlights that the benefit of a high construal level during problem formulation depends on a low construal level during problem framing, offering a more holistic understanding of the strategic decision-making process.

2 | THEORY AND HYPOTHESES

The first step in the strategic decision-making process is the *identification stage*, which sets the stage for the subsequent development, evaluation, and implementation of strategies (Figure 1; Csaszar and Laureiro-Martínez 2018, Mintzberg et al. 1976, Posen et al. 2018). Assuming that a problem has been detected and managers have decided to solve it (“problem finding” in Figure 1), the identification stage involves problem framing and formulation (Ananth et al. 2024, Nickerson et al. 2007). Problem framing involves attention allocation, whereas problem formulation is concerned with theorization or causal judgment (Baer et al. 2013, Park 2024). During problem framing, managers attend to symptoms in a given problem space. Symptoms are the information cues that signify a deviation from expectations, such as the failure to meet performance expectations. Managers then develop theories about the underlying causes that may explain the identified symptoms to orient their search for solutions (Felin and Zenger 2009, Nickerson and Argyres 2018, Posen et al. 2018). Table 1 contains definitions of the key terms in this paper.

INSERT TABLE 1 & FIGURE 1 HERE

Research in the behavioral and knowledge-based views of the firm, as well as the theory-based view of strategy, offers consistent support for the notion that problem formulation is central to the

effective development, evaluation, and implementation of strategies (Camuffo et al. 2020, Nickerson and Zenger 2004, Posen et al. 2018). Without problem formulation, managers likely focus on symptoms without understanding their causes. Nevertheless, problem formulation alone is insufficient to find globally optimum solutions for two reasons. First, managers often identify only a few symptoms, rather than a web of correlated symptoms that collectively and exhaustively describe the problems, curtailing their ability to understand relevant aspects of the problem space (Baer et al. 2013, Gavetti et al. 2012). Second, managers often find local, obvious causes based on the symptoms, rather than developing theories on alternative causes to holistically understand the problem space (Greve 2003, Posen et al. 2018). This narrow formulation, in turn, propels managers to engage in an often-ineffective trial-and-error approach to resolve the problem (Gavetti and Levinthal 2000, Nickerson and Zenger 2004). In essence, managers generate solutions for single, local causes based on a limited understanding of symptoms, test the solutions to see if they work, and then develop new solutions based on what was learned in a prior trial (Camuffo et al. 2020, Zellweger and Zenger 2023). This approach is ineffective because solutions are potentially infinite and resources are constrained in strategic settings, and local search is likely to only identify local peaks (i.e., suboptimal solutions) (Gavetti et al. 2005).

To illustrate, consider the example of an organization that has become the target of a cyberattack. This attack may initially manifest via one obvious symptom – the sudden loss of firm data. Based on this symptom, managers may theorize that passcodes have been leaked and thus decide to change security protocols. However, they may ignore other causes, such as the motives of insiders who are leaking the information (e.g., they are unhappy or unsatisfied with their leaders or their pay), and thus neglect to develop strategies that can eliminate the root cause of the problem. In contrast, if managers identify other, related symptoms, such as the departure of key information technology employees in a short time period, they may also consider these causes and develop more effective strategies.

2.1 | Framing Symptom Count and Formulation Comprehensiveness

In this paper, we maintain that *symptom count*, or the number of symptoms individuals identify during problem framing, is the key criterion for strategic problem framing. Many symptoms that

characterize a strategic problem are not immediately observable (Bhardwaj et al. 2018). If managers frame problems without sufficient symptom count, they are likely to miss or ignore informational cues critical to formulating the problems (Csaszar and Levinthal 2016, Gavetti et al. 2005, Lee and Csaszar 2020). Although resolving symptoms does not automatically lead to effective strategies, identifying a greater number of symptoms is valuable for increasing *comprehensiveness*, which is the criterion for evaluating strategic problem formulation (Baer et al. 2013). Comprehensiveness is defined as the number of alternative, potentially relevant (explaining at least one symptom) causes that collectively explain the identified, correlated symptoms. A comprehensive formulation prevents managers from overlooking potentially central causes (Mitroff and Featheringham 1974). In practice, consultants and analysts in companies like McKinsey have the goal of finding a MECE (mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive) set of factors in problem analysis, which reflects the importance of symptom count and comprehensiveness.

When problems are simpler or more familiar, managers can quickly identify the most important symptoms and the central, “right” causes using existing heuristics without high symptom count or comprehensiveness (Csaszar and Ostler 2020, Gigerenzer et al. 2022, Kahneman and Klein 2009). Indeed, the literature on adaptive heuristics suggests that, insofar as problems are structurally similar to problems that managers have encountered and solved before, they can use fast-and-frugal heuristics (or “simple rules”) to quickly and efficiently formulate and solve problems (Gigerenzer 2008). However, managers are unlikely to possess valid heuristics to find the “right” causes for complex, ill-structured (e.g., strategic) problems (Gigerenzer et al. 2022).

In the context of strategic problems, past studies offer consistent evidence that greater comprehensiveness enhances strategic decision making. For example, large-scale field experiments indicate that developing alternative theories of problems rather than relying on heuristics allows entrepreneurs to efficiently search for valuable solutions (Camuffo et al. 2020, 2024a). A comprehensive view of the problem space can encourage entrepreneurs to develop solutions for what they consider to be central causes rather than solving more obvious causes that “jump out” at them. Even if their initial

solutions to these theorized, central causes fail, entrepreneurs with a comprehensive understanding of the problem can efficiently pivot and solve what they perceive to be the second most important causes. Indeed, in these studies, even the attempt to develop alternative theories was linked to more methodical problem solving, facilitating purposeful and effective strategic decision-making. Moreover, based on 1,600 interviews with 261 decision makers, Valentine et al. (2024) report that developing alternative theories to develop comprehensive formulations can allow for more radical (as opposed to incremental) pivots to find globally valuable solutions. Case studies of decision makers engaged in strategic problem solving also indicate that problem formulation allows managers to avoid local optima and encourages them to systematically search for globally optimal solutions (Ott and Eisenhardt 2020). Finally, simulation studies highlight the importance of identifying diverse and relevant factors contributing to problems when searching for valuable solutions to complex, ill-structured problems (Gavetti and Levinthal 2000, Gavetti et al. 2005, Rivkin and Siggelkow 2003, Siggelkow and Rivkin 2005).

2.2 | Role of Construal Levels in Problem Framing and Formulation

Our theoretical development rests on the baseline prediction that comprehensiveness of strategic problem formulation is likely to increase as a function of greater symptom count. Greater symptom count allows managers to combine these symptoms, giving rise to a greater number of alternative theories, including those that may seem far-fetched or less plausible at first glance. Given the lack of certainty about what may be the “right” causes of strategic problems, combinations of symptoms are critical in allowing managers to explore different possibilities. Building on this prediction, we examine cognitive factors that (1) aid managers in identifying a greater number of symptoms during problem framing and (2) facilitate (i.e., moderate) the positive baseline relationship between symptom count and comprehensiveness during problem formulation. To do so, we draw on construal level theory (Trope and Liberman 2010).

According to this theory, construal levels influence both attention allocation and causal judgment (Trope and Liberman 2010, Wiesenfeld et al. 2017). Cognition at high construal levels is abstract and superordinate, while it is more concrete and subordinate at low construal levels (Reyt and Wiesenfeld

2015). A high construal level is related to thinking in terms of categories rather than exemplars, wholes rather than parts, and ends rather than means (Rim et al. 2013). Categories, wholes, and ends are all superordinate to exemplars, parts, and means, which are subordinate and characteristic of low construal thinking. Construal levels are largely determined by situational variables and, as such, highly variable (Wiesenfeld et al. 2017).

A central mechanism through which construal levels affect outcomes is through influencing psychological distance (Trope et al. 2007). Individuals at a high construal level “step back” from a given phenomenon and attend to or judge events from a greater psychological distance. This greater psychological distance is useful in finding patterns but not in differentiating nuances. A low construal level, on the other hand, allows individuals to “zero in” on a given phenomenon, which helps identify subordinate details but may lead individuals to be stuck in them and fail to see broader patterns.

We maintain that construal levels are integral during problem framing and formulating, because they influence the types of symptoms individuals pay attention to and the types of causes they can identify. Specifically, we maintain that, during problem framing, a low rather than a high construal level encourages attention toward both common and more novel, typically overlooked symptoms. At a low construal level, managers may avoid top-down filtering of symptoms that do not fit into existing schemas (Gilbert et al. 1998, Trope et al. 2007). Instead, a low construal level enables stimulus-driven, bottom-up attention (Ocasio 2011) that does not filter events through existing schemas. This form of attention is likely to help individuals perceive the full range of symptoms, from obvious ones that fit into existing schemas (e.g., deviations from existing key performance indicators) to the less common ones, such as less quantifiable needs and pain points (Grimes and Vogus 2021, Nickerson et al. 2007, Park 2024, von Hippel and von Krogh 2016).

Experimental evidence reports that high construal thinking can encourage narrow and biased attention to events based on schemas, such as focusing on demographic or racial features of job applicants (Milkman et al. 2012, see also McCrea et al. 2012, Wakslak et al. 2006). Schema-driven attention can result in quick pattern recognition and effective action when problems are familiar and available schemas

are valid (Ocasio 2011). However, established schemas are inadequate for strategic problems, which are typically unique and for which existing schemas are incomplete or irrelevant (Camillus 2008).

The importance of a low construal is reflected in the common metaphor about not being able to see the forest for the trees. When individuals look at the forest only from a great distance, they are likely to primarily perceive the more obvious and familiar aspects of the forest based on past experiences. Information cues (i.e., trees) that do not fit into existing understandings of a forest are likely to be ignored (Henderson 2013). However, if the goal is to identify the full range of symptoms, one must walk among the trees at a closer distance, operating at a low construal level. Therefore, we hypothesize:

Hypothesis 1. *Framing strategic problems at a low level of construal (as opposed to a high construal level) enhances symptom count.*

We conceptualize high construal levels as a moderator of the relationship between symptom count and comprehensiveness, because symptoms are the main ingredients that allow managers to theorize about potential causes. Our model maintains that thinking at a high construal level likely improves managers' ability to utilize the identified symptoms, such that they can formulate problems more comprehensively *even with the same number of symptoms*. Framing problems with a high construal level may lead individuals to overlook certain symptoms. However, during problem formulation and once individuals have attended to them and are aware of them, a high construal level is likely to help managers avoid fixating on particular causes and enable them to combine symptoms flexibly to formulate problems more comprehensively.

For example, in early 2020, before COVID-19 was better understood, many doctors observed its symptoms, ranging from high fever, a rapid transmission rate, to a loss of taste. At the time, this set of symptoms did not fit neatly into an existing diagnosis. Doctors who relied on any one symptom in isolation may have diagnosed patients as having the flu or allergies. Only a minority of doctors in early 2020 thought of an explanation accounting for all correlated symptoms collectively – a new pandemic (Lewis 2021). Given that the effects of causes may manifest across various symptoms when problems are

complex, relevant causes may not be identifiable until managers try to explain the set (or subsets) of symptoms at the same time (Rumelt 2011, Simon 1962, 1991).

This combinatory process is likely to be facilitated by a high construal level. Empirical research on construal levels supports our logic. For example, across five experiments, Shani and colleagues (2009) found that individuals at a high construal level were more likely to entertain both more standard explanations as well as more distant ones for a problem. Other experiments have shown that individuals operating at a high construal level are more successful in deriving superordinate factors and principles from descriptive and concrete data (Rim et al. 2013, 2015), even when the data is novel, complex, or conflicting (Jia et al. 2009, Mueller et al. 2014). This flexibility can be useful during strategic problem formulation, by allowing managers to uncover novel and unconventional yet relevant causes that may turn out to be central in explaining the problem at hand. Given our baseline prediction that symptom count is central to comprehensive problem formulations, our moderation hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 2. *A high construal level (compared to a low construal level) moderates the positive relationship between symptom count and comprehensiveness; the relationship is stronger at a high construal level (as opposed to a low construal level).*

Our hypotheses imply that formulating strategic problems with greater comprehensiveness depends on shifting construal from low (during problem framing) to high (during problem formulation) levels. Initially, during strategic problem framing, a low construal level increases symptom count. Symptom count increases formulation comprehensiveness, but this effect is influenced by whether managers shift to a high level of construal as they engage in problem formulation. Summarizing our logic, we propose a positive effect of a construal level shift on the comprehensiveness of problem formulations:

Hypothesis 3. *Shifting construal levels from low (during problem framing) to high (during problem formulation) leads to greater problem formulation comprehensiveness than other combinations of construals.*

Figure 2 summarizes our overall research model and hypotheses. In subsequent sections, we present Studies 1 and 2, which test Hypotheses 1, 2, and 3 in randomized experiments. Study 3 tests

Hypothesis 2 with a sample of executives. Given that our theory focuses on strategic problems, we keep the complexity and ill-structuredness of problems constant in Studies 1 and 2 and focus on managers who are tackling complex, ill-structured problems in Study 3.

INSERT FIGURE 2 HERE

3 | STUDY 1: METHOD

Study 1 is an experiment that utilized a 2 (construal level during problem framing: low vs. high) \times 2 (construal level during problem formulation: low vs. high) between-subjects design. We collected data from 265 working adults in the U.S. using Prolific Academics (*Mean* age = 28.14, gender = 54.89 % men), an online platform that allows researchers to target and recruit research participants. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the four conditions (low-low: 67; low-high: 64; high-low: 64; high-high: 70). To ensure that participants paid sufficient attention to the materials, we included an attention check test at the end of the study. Only one subject failed the test, and the inclusion and exclusion of this participant did not influence our results. We included the subject in all subsequent analyses.

Participants read a case of a doctor-patient interaction around medical noncompliance (see the Online Appendix). Medical noncompliance is a complex, ill-structured problem plaguing the American healthcare system and is of strategic importance to many healthcare and medical providers (Scarlett and Young 2016). The problem contains numerous causes that interact with each other and change over time, and solutions are likely to be multifaceted and require significant investments (Hugtenburg et al. 2013). We chose the case of doctor-patient interaction because it contains several observable behaviors that serve as cues or symptoms of medical noncompliance. The case does not delineate the underlying causes, allowing participants to theorize the causes on their own.

3.1 | Measures and Manipulations

The core instructions for problem framing and formulation tasks were the same across all conditions. The instruction for problem framing was: “Please read the case below and write down the

problems you see—that is, what is going on.” The instruction for problem formulation was: “Now, write down the different factors that contribute to the problems you have identified.”

Two coders blind to the hypotheses counted the number of distinct symptoms (“Symptom Count”) and causes (“Comprehensiveness”) that participants found and theorized. We informed the coders that symptoms referred to information, facts, or data points that are directly observable in the experimental content. We also asked the coders to not include symptoms derived from any assumptions beyond what was observable in the text. For example, if individuals wrote down that the patient had dementia during the problem framing task, we did not count it as a symptom because the case did not mention that the patient had dementia. During problem formulation, however, we considered dementia as a potential cause if participants had identified symptoms (e.g., not taking medicine on time) that plausibly pointed toward dementia as a potential cause. We also ensured that we counted distinct symptoms and not redundant ones when measuring Symptom Count. If, for example, participants wrote that the patient did not show up to the appointments and had many “no shows,” the coders treated the two statements as one symptom (see Table 2). For Symptom Count, interrater reliability per ICC(1) was 0.86. ICC(2, 1) for interrater consistency was 0.93. ICC(1) and ICC(2, 1) for comprehensiveness were 0.79 and 0.88, respectively.

INSERT TABLE 2 HERE

We manipulated construal levels twice—first during problem framing and then again during problem formulation. This design enabled us to separate the effects of (1) construal level on symptom count during problem framing from the effect of (2) symptom count and construal level on problem formulation comprehensiveness. Consistent with previous research, we manipulated construal levels by adding different linguistic cues to the core instructions to alter individuals’ construal levels during the tasks (Trope and Liberman 2010).

For the *problem framing task*, we gave additional instructions at the end of our core instruction based on the construal level condition. In the low construal level condition, we stated, “Remember to

focus on concrete actions and details—what individuals actually do that is problematic.” In the high construal level condition, we stated, “Please take a big-picture view and ask yourself, more generally, which actions and behaviors deviate from your expectations.” For the *problem formulation task*, we added to the core instruction in the low construal level condition, “Please think about the concrete behaviors that individuals in the case engaged in and the details of the case. You can build on your previous work in addressing this issue.” In the high construal level condition, we added, “Please take a big-picture approach and ask yourself where this issue is really coming from. You can build on your previous work in addressing this issue.”

Finally, we asked three questions to evaluate the effectiveness of our construal level manipulations, consistent with past research (Henderson 2013). Participants responded to the following prompt, “When I answered the question above, I was concerned with...,” followed by “The forest rather than the trees,” “Why the patient was noncompliant rather than how the patient was noncompliant,” and “The general phenomena rather than specific details.” Participants used a response scale that ranged from 1 = *Strongly Disagree* to 7 = *Strongly Agree*. Cronbach’s alpha was 0.65 after problem framing and 0.69 after problem formulation.

3.2 | Results and Discussion

We first examined manipulation checks. Results indicate that the construal level manipulation was successful. For the problem framing task, the high construal level manipulation increased self-reported construal level (difference in *Mean* = 0.70, 95 % confidence interval = [0.42, 0.98], $t(259.96) = 4.96$, $p < 0.01$, effect size or Cohen’s $d = 0.61$). For the problem formulation task, the high construal level manipulation increased self-reported construal level (difference in *Mean* = 0.64, 95 % confidence interval = [0.34, 0.94], $t(260.72) = 4.20$, $p < 0.01$, $d = 0.52$).

Descriptive statistics and correlations displayed in Table 3 reveal no estimation concerns. The Online Appendix contains the balance table for Symptom Count and Comprehensiveness across conditions (Table O1). Given that Symptom Count did not follow a normal distribution (Figure O1 in the Online Appendix), we conducted the two-sided nonparametric Wilcoxon rank sum test to examine

Hypothesis 1. The test supports our Hypothesis that participants in the low construal level condition identified more symptoms compared to participants in the high construal level condition ($W = 13006$, $p < .01$). We further assessed the average Symptom Count in the construal level conditions during problem framing. We found participants in the low construal level condition identified more symptoms during framing ($Mean = 2.92$, $SD = 1.83$) compared to participants in the high construal level condition ($Mean = 1.43$, $SD = 1.22$). Participants in the low construal level condition identified 1.49 more symptoms, a 104 percent increase, compared to participants in the high construal level condition. These findings indicate that we cannot reject Hypothesis 1.

INSERT TABLE 3 HERE

To test Hypothesis 2, we conducted rank sum ANCOVA with Symptom Count as the covariate, given the non-normal distribution of Symptom Count and Comprehensiveness (see Figures O1 and O2 in the Online Appendix).³ Consistent with our baseline prediction, a model including construal level during problem formulation and Symptom Count (without their interaction) returns a main effect for Symptom Count ($F(1, 262) = 97.68$, $p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.27$) and high construal level ($F(1, 262) = 5.28$, $p = 0.02$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$) on Comprehensiveness. A two-way ANCOVA including the interaction between high construal level and Symptom Count revealed a main effect for Symptom Count ($F(1, 261) = 99.76$, $p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.28$) and a main effect for high construal level ($F(1, 261) = 5.39$, $p = 0.02$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$) on Comprehensiveness. Consistent with Hypothesis 2, we found an interaction between high construal level and Symptom Count ($F(1, 261) = 6.58$, $p = 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$).⁴ The model comparison test reports that the model with the interaction is a significantly better fit than the one without it ($p = 0.01$). Simple slope tests revealed a significant positive relationship between Symptom Count and

³ We also ran rank sum ANCOVA including demographic control variables (age and gender) when testing Hypothesis 2 for Studies 1 and 2. The inclusion of these variables does not affect the patterns of results, so we report results excluding demographic variables. We also ran ANCOVA along with rank sum ANCOVA and the results without rank sum are consistent with those of the reported results.

⁴ To evaluate whether outliers unduly influenced our result, we repeated our analysis excluding observations with a Cook's distance that was at least three times above the mean. Results remain unchanged, with the interaction term having a significant effect on comprehensiveness ($F(1, 249) = 4.53$, $p = 0.03$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.02$).

Comprehensiveness both when the construal level was high ($b = 0.69, SE = 0.06, p < 0.01$) and when it was low ($b = 0.35, SE = 0.09, p < 0.01$) (see Figure 3). Thus, we cannot reject Hypothesis 2.

INSERT FIGURE 3 HERE

To test Hypothesis 3, we conducted pairwise comparisons of Comprehensiveness across the four conditions. Individuals who shifted their construal from low to high formulated the problem with greater Comprehensiveness ($Mean = 3.41, SD = 1.97$) than participants who operated at a low construal level during framing and formulation ($Mean = 2.53, SD = 1.54$, two-sided Wilcoxon rank sum test statistic $W = 2687.50, p = 0.01$), participants who remained at a high construal level during framing and formulation ($Mean = 2.61, SD = 2.14, W = 2700.50, p = 0.04$), and participants who shifted from high to low construal levels between framing and formulation ($Mean = 2.52, SD = 2.11, W = 2572.50, p = 0.01$). The means of Comprehensiveness across the other three groups were not significantly different from each other ($ps > 0.68$). Participants who shifted their construal from low to high formulated problems with 30 percent greater comprehensiveness compared to participants who did not. Thus, we cannot reject Hypothesis 3.

In a post hoc analysis, we checked an assumption underlying our model. Our model assumes that a low construal level allows managers to identify more novel symptoms – symptoms that other managers may fail to identify. Our model also assumes that a high construal allows managers to identify novel causes that other managers may fail to consider, given the same numbers of symptoms. The identification of novel symptoms and causes as well as obvious ones allow for greater symptom count and comprehensiveness. We thus tested the relationships between symptom count and novelty of problem frames and between comprehensiveness and novelty of problem formulations.

To rate Novelty of problem framing, a coder who was not involved in the evaluation of other measures rated the relative frequency with which specific symptoms were identified. The coder relied on a Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *Not at all novel* (highly frequently identified across the entire sample) to 5 = *Highly novel* (highly unconventional). Consistent with our expectations, we found that Symptom Count was positively related to Novelty of problem frames (Spearman's rank correlation $\rho = 0.47, p <$

0.01)⁵. We asked another coder who was not involved in the evaluation of other measures to code for Novelty of problem formulations. The coder relied on a Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *Not at all novel* (highly frequently identified) to 5 = *Highly novel* (unconventional). Consistent with our expectations, we found that Comprehensiveness was positively related to the Novelty of problem formulations ($\rho = 0.41, p < 0.01$).

The results from Study 1 are consistent with our hypotheses. Low construal level thinking encourages individuals to frame strategic problems with greater symptom counts. Greater symptom counts, in turn, enhance the range of potential causes they consider, both familiar and novel. Still, this study has two limitations. First, part of our construal level manipulation was embedded into the task instructions. Although this choice is consistent with previous research (Burgoon et al. 2013), it may have influenced both individuals' cognition (as intended) and the task approach (not intended). Moreover, the study does not rely on a managerial sample and does not employ a more traditional business problem. In Study 2, we tested our model in a managerial sample, addressing a more typical strategic problem. In addition, we refined our manipulation of construal levels.

4 | STUDY 2: METHOD

We collected data from 181 mid- and high-level managers of large corporations through Prolific (*Mean age = 36.17, gender = 38 % female*). Participants were pooled from a sample of individuals who reported that they were working in companies with more than 250 employees and that they had direct managerial experience. Participants were compensated for their time following Prolific's guidelines. Like Study 1, Study 2 employed a 2 (construal level during problem framing: low vs. high) \times 2 (construal level during problem formulation: low vs. high) between-subjects design. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the four experimental conditions (low-low: 43; low-high: 46; high-low: 46; high-high: 46).

⁵ Along with the nonparametric tests, we also conducted linear regressions for post hoc analyses. The results from linear regressions are consistent with the reported results, which are more conservative and do not rely on the normality assumption of the distributions of the data or residuals.

Following Csaszar and Laureiro-Martínez (2018), we invited participants to watch a video from the *Kickstarter.com* platform (an online platform that allows individuals or groups to raise money for their ventures). The video described a firm that had failed to reach its funding goal, deliver the product on time, and attract customers' attention even after the product launched (for more details, see Csaszar and Laureiro-Martínez 2018). After watching the video, we asked participants to frame and formulate the firm's strategic problem. We included an attention check question at the end of the study, asking participants to identify the mode of transportation primarily featured in the video (bicycles). The inclusion or exclusion of the two subjects who did not pass the attention check did not significantly change our results. Thus, we retained all participants for our analysis.

4.1 | Measures and Manipulations

The instructions for the problem framing and formulation tasks were the same across all conditions. For problem framing, we told participants: "The project attempted to raise funds through crowdsourcing but failed to reach its funding goal or to attract customers after the product was launched. Please imagine that you are a leader of [company name] trying to understand what was potentially wrong with the product or the promotional video. Please write down the problems you see, that is, what seems problematic about the product or the video." For problem formulation, we told participants: "Now, please write down the different factors that may be contributing to the problems you have identified for [company name]. What do you think might be potentially contributing to the problems?"

Two coders blind to the hypotheses counted the number of distinct symptoms ("Symptom Count") and potential causes ("Comprehensiveness") that participants identified. Similar to Study 1, we informed the coders that symptoms referred to information, facts, or data points that are directly observable in the video (see Table 2). We also asked the coders to not include symptoms derived from any assumptions beyond what was observable in the text. For Symptom Count, ICC(1) was 0.91. ICC(2, 1) was 0.95. ICC(1) and ICC(2, 1) for Comprehensiveness were 0.88 and 0.94, respectively.

We manipulated construal levels by asking participants a set of questions before framing and formulating the strategic problem. This approach to manipulating construal levels allowed us to keep the

actual instructions for problem framing and formulation consistent across conditions, thereby addressing a potential shortcoming of Study 1. Specifically, we manipulated construal levels by asking participants a set of *how* (to induce a low construal level) or *why* (to induce a high construal level) questions. *How* questions encourage people to think more concretely about subordinate details; *why* questions cause people to think more abstractly about superordinate factors (Burrus and Roesse 2006). This manipulation is one of the most widely used and validated approaches to manipulating construal levels (Burgoon et al. 2013).

To illustrate, participants in the high construal level condition for problem framing answered *why* they might like to improve their health and performance at work before completing the problem framing task. Participants in the high construal level condition for problem formulation answered *why* they might want to improve their attentional focus while working and *why* they might want to improve their communication skills before completing the problem formulation task. Participants in the low construal level condition were asked *how* to accomplish these objectives. Participants had to answer each question four times consecutively at increasing levels of abstraction or concreteness—for example, if they stated that they would like to improve their health because they wanted to live longer, we then asked them why they would like to live longer, and so on. We conducted a manipulation check by examining the answers to the two sets of prompts. Two subjects failed to answer the questions in logically consistent and unambiguous ways (e.g., “buying gym courses” as a *how* to improve communication skills). Since excluding these participants did not change our results, we retained them in our analysis.

4.2 | Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics and correlations displayed in Table 4 reveal no estimation concerns. Table O2 contains the balance table across the conditions for Symptom Count and Comprehensiveness. To test Hypothesis 1, we compared Symptom Count during problem framing across the high and low construal level conditions. Given the non-normal distribution of Symptom Count (see Figure O3 in the Online Appendix), we relied on a nonparametric rank sum test as we did for Study 1. Participants in the low construal level condition framed problems with greater Symptom Count ($Mean = 3.32, SD = 1.50$)

compared to participants in the high construal level condition ($Mean = 2.31, SD = 1.10$) ($W = 5634, p < 0.01$). Participants in the low construal level condition identified 1.01 more symptoms, a 44 percent increase, compared to participants in the high construal level condition. Thus, we cannot reject Hypothesis 1.

INSERT TABLE 4 HERE

To test Hypothesis 2, we conducted ranked-sum ANCOVA given the non-normal distribution of Symptom Count and Comprehensiveness (see Figure O4 in the Online Appendix). A two-way model without the interaction between construal level during problem formulation and Symptom Count revealed a main effect of Symptom Count ($F(1, 178) = 35.12, p < 0.01, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.15$) and a main effect of high construal level ($F(178, 1) = 9.10, p < 0.01, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.05$) on Comprehensiveness. A model including the interaction between construal level and Symptom Count reveals a main effect of Symptom Count ($F(1, 177) = 35.91, p < 0.01, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.15$) and high construal level ($F(1, 177) = 9.30, p < 0.01, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.05$). Consistent with Hypothesis 2, we found a significant interaction between high construal level and Symptom Count on Comprehensiveness ($F(1, 177) = 4.97, p = 0.03, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.03$).⁶ The model comparison test reveals that the model with the interaction is a significantly better fit than the one without it, $p = 0.03$. Simple slope analysis revealed that Symptom Count had a significant effect on Comprehensiveness when the construal level was high ($b = 0.43, SE = 5.01, p < 0.01$) and when it was low ($b = 0.32, SE = 0.10, p = 0.03$) (see Figure 4). Thus, we cannot reject Hypothesis 2.

INSERT FIGURE 4 HERE

To test Hypothesis 3, we conducted pairwise comparisons of Comprehensiveness to test whether participants in the low-to-high construal level (construal shift) condition formulated problems with the greatest comprehensiveness, as opposed to participants in the other three conditions. We find that the

⁶ To evaluate whether outliers unduly influenced our result, we repeated our analysis excluding observations with a Cook's distance that was at least three times above the mean. Results remain unchanged, with the interaction term having a significant effect on comprehensiveness ($F(1, 167) = 5.70, p = 0.02, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.03$).

participants in the construal shift condition formulated problems with greater Comprehensiveness ($Mean = 2.01, SD = 1.08$) than participants who operated at a low construal level during both framing and formulation ($Mean = 1.12, SD = 1.35$, two-sided Wilcoxon rank sum test statistic $W = 1476, p < 0.01$), participants who remained at a high construal level during both framing and formulation ($Mean = 1.27, SD = 1.06, W = 1457.50, p < 0.01$), and participants who shifted from high to low construal levels between framing and formulation ($Mean = 1.16, W = 1506, p < 0.01$). Participants who shifted construal levels from low to high formulated their problem with 58 percent more comprehensiveness compared to other participants. Comprehensiveness did not differ significantly among the three other groups ($ps > 0.23$ for all analyses).

In a post hoc analysis, we again tested the relationship between Symptom Count and Novelty of problem frames, and between Comprehensiveness and Novelty of problem formulations. We asked a coder who was not involved in the evaluation of other measures to first go through all problem frames and evaluate the relative frequency with which specific symptoms were identified to rate Novelty of problem frames. The coder relied on a Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *Not at all novel* (highly frequently identified) to 5 = *Highly novel* (unconventional). Consistent with our expectations, we found that Symptom Count was positively related to Novelty of problem frames (Spearman's rank correlation $\rho = 0.19, p = 0.01$). We asked another coder who was not involved in the evaluation of other measures to code for Novelty of problem formulations on a Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *Not at all novel* (highly frequently identified) to 5 = *Highly novel* (unconventional). Consistent with our expectations, we found that Comprehensiveness was positively related to the Novelty of problem formulations ($\rho = 0.25, p < 0.01$).

Compared to Study 1, Study 2 used a different approach to manipulating construal levels, utilized a real-world strategic problem, and relied on a sample of mid- to high-level managers. Despite these differences, we again find evidence consistent with our hypotheses. The results indicate that construal levels rather than the specific instructions used in Study 1 drive our results and that our model is robust across different problems and samples. However, Studies 1 and 2 have another limitation. Managers in work settings may have greater time to think about their strategic problems and potentially incubate ideas

on how to address them (Dane and Pratt 2009, Shin and Grant 2021). During this incubation process, managers may come upon alternative causes and formulate problems more comprehensively without the need for high construal level thinking. Indeed, many strategic problems persist and allow for incubation as managers contemplate the various causes of a problem. Whether construal level interacts with symptom count to improve comprehensiveness (Hypothesis 2) over time may be thus important to verify. Accordingly, we conducted a field study in which managers were tasked with formulating their firms' strategic problems after having framed them some time prior, allowing for potential incubation.

5 | STUDY 3: METHOD

Study 3 involves a sample of executives from firms in the consumer sector in China—mostly selling products and services on the Chinese e-commerce platform Taobao—to specifically test Hypothesis 2. This study is based on questionnaires distributed and collected during a conference. The conference organizers asked executives to frame problems in their organizations *before* attending the conference, which allowed us to evaluate the benefit of high construal level even when managers had time to incubate while formulating the problems.

The conference's focus was for executives to reflect on the problems they had experienced in achieving their performance goals during 2020 and to develop new strategies for 2021. Conference organizers handed out surveys to participants as they registered for the conference. The actual conference began on the second day. The organizer collected completed surveys from the point of registration to just before the conference formally started, preventing the conference's content from unduly influencing responses. Among the 314 conference attendees, 128 completed the survey (Mean age = 37.91, gender = 41.41 % women). The response rate (40.76 %) is similar to previous studies using Chinese executives (Atuahene-Gima and Li 2004).

5.1 | Task and Measures

Strategic problem framing Symptom Count was measured based on conference attendees' reports of the symptoms they had noticed during 2020, which were preventing their firms from achieving their performance aspirations. During the conference, we asked participants to outline the “potential causes that

can explain the symptoms” (i.e., formulate the problems). Along with the control variables we list below, we also asked respondents to self-report their construal levels with which they formulated their strategic problems. Two conference organizers who were blind to the hypotheses counted the number of symptoms (“Symptom Count”) and the number of causes (“Comprehensiveness”) listed by each respondent. To ensure that the organizers counted only *relevant* causes, we instructed them to only consider causes that appeared plausible given the symptoms the respondents had listed. ICC(1) was 0.78 and ICC(2, 1) was 0.87 for Symptom Count. ICC(1) was 0.70 and ICC(2, 1) was 0.83 for Comprehensiveness. Rater counts were averaged.

We used established measures to assess construal level (“Construal”) during problem formulation (Burrus and Roesse 2006). The exact questions are listed in the Online Appendix. Cronbach’s alpha was 0.63, indicating moderate reliability of the items (Lance et al. 2006). In our analyses, we controlled for *demand uncertainty* and *technology uncertainty* (Atuahene-Gima and Li 2004), which are likely to differ across firms. Demand uncertainty (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.74) is the perceived unpredictability of customers’ demands. Technology uncertainty (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.83) is the perceived unpredictability in the technology underlying the industry. The exact questions for these measures are listed in the Online Appendix. We also included other demographic and knowledge-related covariates. Demographic covariates included *gender* (1 = women) and *age*. The knowledge-related covariate was breadth of knowledge, measured via the number of industries the executives had worked in (Gavetti et al. 2005, Mannucci and Yong 2018).

5.2 | Study 3: Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics and correlations listed in Table 5 reveal no estimation concerns. Table 6 presents the regression results. Model 1 includes only control variables. Model 2 adds Symptom Count and Construal. Model 3 adds the interaction between Symptom Count and Construal⁷. Consistent with Hypothesis 2, adding the interaction term improves the model’s fit, increasing log-likelihood from -

⁷ The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test on the residuals of the regression reports a test statistic of 0.07, $p = 0.51$, which justifies the use of linear regressions to test Hypothesis 2.

175.69 to -172.90 ($\chi^2(1) = 5.57, p = 0.02$). Model 3 offers weak evidence for the direct effect of Symptom Count ($b = -0.69, SE = 0.39, p = 0.08$) and no evidence for a direct effect of Construal ($b = -0.54, SE = 0.38, p = 0.16$) on Comprehensiveness. Importantly, the effect of the interaction between Symptom Count and Construal on Comprehensiveness is significant ($b = 0.21, SE = 0.09, p = 0.02$, see Figure 5 for a model with the control variables and Table O5 in the Online Appendix for a model without the control variables).⁸⁹ The effect size of the interaction term (Cohen's f^2) is 0.10, indicating a small-to-medium effect size. Finally, simple slope analysis provides results that are consistent with Hypothesis 2. The relationship between Symptom Count and Comprehensiveness was significant when construal level was high (+1 *SD*) ($b = 0.31, SE = 0.08, t(125) = 3.85, p < 0.01$) and when it was at the mean ($b = 0.20, SE = 0.06, t(125) = 3.49, p < 0.01$) but not when construal level was low (-1 *SD*) ($b = 0.09, SE = 0.07, t(125) = 1.17, p = 0.24$). Thus, we cannot reject Hypothesis 2.

INSERT TABLES 5 & 6 & FIGURE 5 HERE

As a post hoc analysis, we evaluated the relationship between Comprehensiveness and Novelty of problem formulation. We asked a coder who was not involved in the evaluation of other measures in this study to rate Novelty of problem formulations submitted for the study (on a Likert scale, ranging from 1 = *Not at all novel* to 5 = *Highly novel*). Consistent with our expectations, we found that Comprehensiveness was positively related to Novelty of problem formulations ($\rho = 0.45, p < 0.01$). Given that this study did not allow us to control for the content of strategic problems, we did not feel comfortable evaluating whether managers had identified symptoms that were often overlooked by other managers in the same problem space. We were more confident in evaluating the novelty of problem formulations, because many

⁸ To evaluate whether outliers unduly influenced our result, we repeated our analysis excluding observations with a Cook's distance that was at least three times above the mean. Results remain unchanged, with the interaction term having a significant effect on comprehensiveness ($b = 0.23, SE = 0.10, p = 0.03$).

⁹ Although our dependent variable is based on counts of causes, we are not able to run Poisson regression because the final measure of comprehensiveness is based on the average between two coders and many observations had non-integer values. To account for the skewness of the data, we instead ran a gamma regression as a robustness check. The result from the gamma regression is consistent with the reported results. Notably, the interaction between Symptom Count and Construal is significant ($b = 0.07, SE = 0.03, p = 0.03$).

managers identified similar causes (e.g., COVID-19 and related challenges in international relations and trades) given the time frame of the study. We thus did not measure the novelty of problem framing.

Study 3 relied on a sample of executives analyzing strategic problems they had been wrestling with for some time, addressing the limitations of Studies 1 and 2. Despite the differences in study design, Study 3 again reports evidence consistent with Hypothesis 2. The results from the three studies are consistent with our logic that comprehensive problem formulations, generated via greater symptom count and high construal levels tend to include more novel causes.

6 | DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

6.1 | Contributions

Our construal level shift model highlights the importance of construal levels as cognitive factors that drive and support the framing and formulation of strategic problems. In essence, to see the “forest” of a strategic problem, managers benefit from first operating at a low construal level to identify the symptoms or “trees.” Once managers have attended to the symptoms, they benefit from stepping back via a high construal level to flexibly theorize potential causes that may explain identified symptoms. Otherwise, managers may only perceive familiar symptoms based on available schemas or fail to combine the symptoms to formulate the problem comprehensively.

Our results are consistent with prior research, which theorizes or reports that high construal thinking facilitates problem formulation comprehensiveness (Cummings and Nickerson 2024, Park and Baer 2022). However, the present research extends Park and Baer (2022), which ignored problem framing. The present paper identifies a low construal level as critical for managers to frame problems with greater nuance. In doing so, this paper highlights the importance of the timing of abstract thinking. Based on the findings of previous research, one could have assumed that managers should use abstract, big-picture thinking from the start of the strategic decision-making process. Our studies indicate that the benefit of abstract thinking depends on first identifying the symptoms characterizing strategic problems using a low construal level.

Our research contributes to the behavioral and attention-based view of the firm (Ocasio 2011, Posen et al. 2018). The behavioral view of the firm maintains that managers attend to problems based on bottom-up attention, in response to performance feedback. The attention-based view theorizes different effects of top-down thinking as well as bottom-up thinking for noticing opportunities and environmental changes (Shepherd et al. 2017). Yet, this view takes an either-or approach, examining the distinct effects of either top-down or bottom-up thinking on different outcomes. What these bodies of research have not examined is how bottom-up and top-down processes may be sequenced during phases of an activity to deliver better outcomes. Our paper highlights how a unique combination of bottom-up attention and top-down theorization helps avoid potential pitfalls when formulating strategic problems.

Moreover, our paper contributes to the knowledge-based view of the firm (in particular, the problem-solving perspective, Nickerson and Zenger 2004) and the theory-based view of strategy (Camuffo et al. 2020). In these streams of research, entrepreneurial success, knowledge creation, and innovation in strategic contexts depend on comprehensive and novel formulations of problems (Camuffo et al. 2024b, Nickerson and Argyres 2018, Park, 2024). Although both streams of research recognize that problem framing and formulation activities are key to developing such formulations (Camuffo et al. 2020, 2024a, Nickerson et al. 2007), how to effectively engage these activities in various contexts remains an open question. Past research also does not elaborate on the relationships between these activities, which are often not properly distinguished (Ananth et al. 2024). Our paper investigates the underlying interdependencies between the activities and provides an understanding of how managers may engage them to achieve greater comprehensiveness.

Our construal level shift model contributes to managerial cognition research and construal level theory. Our model challenges past research, which has tended to adopt an “either-or” approach, examining whether one form of cognition is more effective for a desired outcome than another (Alaybek et al. 2022). We advance a more nuanced, “both-and” approach to managerial cognition that examines how distinct forms of cognition may be combined for superior outcomes (Park 2024). This insight is valuable for emerging research on construal level shifts in particular (Steinbach et al. 2019). Available

construal level shift models emphasize the shift from high to low construal (Carton 2018) during strategic decision making, as a low construal level is linked to implementation. Extending research on attention, we highlight how the shift from a low to a high construal (and back to a low construal for implementation) may be key to effective strategic decision making.

Finally, our post hoc analysis indicates that comprehensiveness and novelty of problem formulations do not necessarily preclude one another. One question in past research is whether the pursuit of comprehensiveness would result in managers finding many obvious causes (related to exploitation) rather than exploring novel causes (related to exploration, Park 2024). Our results indicate that the pursuit of comprehensiveness may be centrally linked to finding both obvious and novel causes. Our insight is consistent with findings in creativity research, in which one of the most robust drivers of novelty in ideas is the number of ideas developed (Harvey and Rietzschel 2022).

6.2 | Limitations

Our paper has several limitations. First, our model is far from comprehensive. For example, the model likely simplifies the relationship between symptom count and comprehensiveness. Although our paper treats the relationship as linear and positive, identifying an ever-increasing number of symptoms may result in diminishing returns in improving comprehensiveness by producing information overload. The literature on information overload demonstrates that processing too much information leads to “chunking” – clustering information based on obvious commonalities (Allred et al. 2016, Gobet et al. 2001). Chunking is bound to result in information loss, as nuance is replaced with a focus on apparent similarities (Thalman et al. 2019). When the number of symptoms exceeds certain levels, the loss of information due to chunking likely degrades the problem formulation activity and decreases comprehensiveness. We also assume, based on past research, a baseline level of epistemic motivation (footnote 2). Future researchers may want to explicitly test the role of epistemic motivation during the construal level shift and explore other individual level variables, such as affective states that may affect problem formulation comprehensiveness.

Second, our paper adopts the individual as the unit of analysis. Although individual managers typically initiate the strategic decision-making process, the process can involve groups of individuals over time (Baer et al. 2013, Lyles and Mitroff 1980). The use of groups notwithstanding, we maintain that the individual level of analysis provides a robust cognitive foundation for developing more sophisticated models at higher levels of analysis. For example, the challenges that individuals encounter when framing and formulating complex, ill-structured problems may shape the design of team processes (Park et al. 2023). Top management or mid-level management teams may distribute strategic problem framing and formulation tasks to different members so that no single member has to do both (see Peña and Parshall 2001). In addition, groups may adopt specific processes that allow for systematic inducement and shifts in construal levels during the two activities (Cummings and Nickerson 2024). Our studies do not explore how managers and groups learn when and how to shift their construal levels.

Third, we do not examine how managers may iterate or cycle between problem framing and formulation during problem solving. While we treat problem framing and formulation as unfolding linearly, managers may return to framing after they start formulating the problem (e.g., when the identified causes suggest the inclusion of additional symptoms). While our model does not directly address this possibility, the more managers understand the importance of the requisite construal levels for problem framing and formulation, the better they may perform these activities. Our model can thereby reduce the likelihood of having to cycle back to problem framing. Even when managers cycle back, our model offers insights into the importance of adopting low construals when returning to problem framing. We encourage scholars to empirically test the importance of construal levels when managers engage cyclically in problem framing and formulation.

Fourth, future researchers may offer greater precision by distinguishing the effects of construal levels from those of psychological distance. Distinguishing these effects is difficult, because they are conceptually closely related and have bidirectional relationships (Rim et al. 2013, Wiesenfeld et al. 2017). However, a low or high construal level may be inherently adaptive in thinking about symptoms or causes, even without the mechanism of psychological distance. Construal level scholars note that high and low

construal levels are about thinking in terms of superordinate and subordinate factors, including ends and means (Rim et al. 2013). Symptoms may be conceptualized as a means to reach causes that are the ends that managers ultimately seek. Hence, in addition to our theorized mechanism of psychological distance, construal levels may also increase symptom count or comprehensiveness without altering psychological distance. To improve precision in theory, we encourage future scholars to rely on neurological analysis to isolate the effects of psychological distance from construal levels to offer more precise insights.

Finally, one potential criticism of comprehensive problem formulations may be that it is akin to merely creating a laundry list of causes. Yet, this apparently simple task is difficult in practice. Past research indicates that individuals who are aware of or are asked to identify multiple causes of complex problems (with a large number of symptoms) still oversimplify their problem formulations (Park and Baer 2022). Indeed, von Hippel and von Krogh (2016) highlight that formulating complex and ill-structured problems is so challenging and cognitively difficult that managers may benefit from avoiding the activity altogether. We thus maintain that the task of developing comprehensive problem formulations is a nontrivial task. Our paper is valuable in examining a process to relax cognitive constraints that can impede individuals from creating a comprehensive list of causes.

6.3 | Practical implications

Our construal level shift model of problem framing and formulating is relevant to the practice of strategic decision making. First, our model indicates that managers benefit from separately engaging in framing and formulating. Although these activities and their outcomes are related, trying to conduct them simultaneously likely results in managers either compromising the framing activity or reducing comprehensiveness, because individuals cannot simultaneously use both high and low levels of construal. Thus, strategic decision makers might want to set aside time to separately engage in framing and formulating and adopt appropriate construal levels for these activities. Second, construal level theory maintains that individuals can easily shift between construal levels with instructions (e.g., why and how questions) and in response to certain situational factors (Henderson 2013). These insights could allow managers to design theoretically sound, effective, and easy-to-implement processes that cause the

important shift in construal levels, thereby supporting the development of comprehensive problem formulations, in accordance, for example, with McKinsey's MECE principle.

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Figure 1. Strategic Decision-Making Process

Figure 2. Research Model

Figure 3. Interaction between Construal Level and Symptom Count on Comprehensiveness, Study 1

Figure 4. Interaction between Construal Level and Symptom Count on Comprehensiveness, Study 2

Figure 5. Interaction between Construal Level and Symptom Count on Comprehensiveness, with control variables, Study 3

Table 1. Constructs, Definitions, and Illustrative Examples

Construct	Definition
Strategic problem framing	Identifying symptoms (deviations from performance expectations) that characterize the strategic problem
Problem framing symptom count	Number of symptoms
Strategic problem formulation	Identifying relevant causes to explain all previously identified symptoms
Problem formulation comprehensiveness	Number of potentially relevant, theorized causes

Table 2. Examples of Symptoms and Causes Identified during Problem Framing and Problem Formulation, Studies 1 and 2

Study	Problem Framing	Problem Formulation
Study 1	<p>Low symptom count: “The patient has severe heart conditions.” (1 symptom)</p> <p>High symptom count: “uncontrolled hypertension/elevated cholesterol/diabetes/noncompliance and no shows/documentation was sparse and often illegible/patient did not follow up on cardiologist referral and doctor did not follow up/ patient inconsistent in taking blood pressure medication/patient distrusts doctors and pharmaceutical companies...” (8 symptoms)</p>	<p>Low comprehensiveness: “I think the patient probably ate badly all their life and then the problems compound themselves with aging” (2 causes)</p> <p>High comprehensiveness: “The patient may have felt they were not getting the treatment they needed and they could have had a bad experience in the past which made them miss appointments. The patient’s behaviors could also be age related as memory loss, aggression, etc. could be a sign of something such as dementia. The doctor may be under pressure and focused on other patients instead...” (6 causes)</p>
Study 2	<p>Low symptom count: “I don’t like the design of the helmet.” (1 symptom)</p> <p>High symptom count: “There’s no charisma in this video, people seem friendly but what they say is really vague and sounds like a script from a school textbook. Music doesn’t fit that profile of a new, innovative, potentially breakthrough product. There is this supposedly cool tech that allows some things but it’s not really explained.” (4 symptoms)</p>	<p>Low comprehensiveness: “Lack of market research.” (1 cause)</p> <p>High comprehensiveness: “Lack of focus or clear goal in what the product should be, lack of product-market fit, lack of insights on customers and artistic vision to design good videos. Perhaps all because the team lacked fund and/or time” (4 causes)</p>

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics and Correlations, Study 1

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Symptom Count	2.17	1.72					
2. Comprehensiveness	2.76	1.98	0.45***				
3. Gender	1.46	0.54	0.12*	0.05			
4. Age	28.14	10.83	0.15*	0.11	0.17*		
5. Construal 1	0.51	0.50	-0.43***	-0.11	0.04	-0.04	
6. Construal 2	0.51	0.50	-0.01	0.12	0.13*	0.05	0.03

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics and Correlations, Study 2

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Symptom Count	2.81	1.40					
2. Comprehensiveness	1.40	1.18	0.38***				
3. Gender	1.38	0.49	0.02	0.09			
4. Age	36.17	10.80	0.05	0.07	-0.12		
5. Construal 1	0.51	0.50	-0.36***	-0.15	-0.06	0.03	
6. Construal 2	0.51	0.50	0.13	0.21*	-0.04	-0.03	-0.02

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics and Correlations, Study 3

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Comprehensiveness	2.82	1.02							
2. Gender	0.41	0.49	0.08						
3. Age	37.91	6.25	0.12	0.00					
4. Technology uncertainty	4.16	0.67	0.06	-0.01	0.17				
5. Demand uncertainty	4.28	0.55	0.03	-0.03	0.07	0.41***			
6. Breadth of knowledge	2.06	1.00	0.10	-0.07	0.22*	0.10	0.19*		
7. Symptom Count	3.52	1.51	0.27**	0.06	0.15	0.15	0.07	-0.09	
8. Construal	4.16	0.57	0.10	0.05	-0.07	0.07	0.15	-0.05	-0.11

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 6. Regression Results for Strategic Problem Formulation Comprehensiveness, Study 3

Variable	Model 1		Model 2		Model 2	
	\hat{b} (SE)	<i>p</i>	\hat{b} (SE)	<i>p</i>	\hat{b} (SE)	<i>p</i>
<i>Control variables</i>						
Gender	0.17 (0.18)	0.35	0.13 (0.18)	0.48	0.17 (0.18)	0.33
Age	0.02 (0.02)	0.30	0.01 (0.01)	0.48	0.01 (0.01)	0.44
Demand uncertainty	-0.01 (0.18)	0.97	-0.07 (0.18)	0.69	-0.06 (0.18)	0.73
Technology uncertainty	0.06 (0.15)	0.69	0.00 (0.15)	0.99	-0.01 (0.14)	0.93
Breadth of knowledge	0.08 (0.09)	0.87	0.13 (0.09)	0.16	0.14 (0.09)	0.12
<i>Main variables</i>						
Symptom Count			0.19 (0.06)	0.00	-0.69 (0.39)	0.08
Construal			0.26 (0.16)	0.10	-0.54 (0.38)	0.16
<i>Interactions</i>						
Symptom Count × Construal					0.21 (0.09)	0.02
Constant	1.76 (0.91)	0.07	0.64 (1.04)	0.54	3.88 (1.75)	0.03
Observations	128		128		128	
F-statistic	0.72		2.24		2.69	
<i>R</i> ²	0.03		0.12		0.15	
Log-likelihood	-181.66		-175.69		-172.90	